

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE X

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

October 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300
pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639684666397

*"Write. Educate.
Connect."*

 @pinagpalapublishingservices **Search**

 pinagpala_publishing **Search**

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com **Search**

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), pp.69-77, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Maria Aillen Valenzona Alkuino-Cabahug (MAVAC) Technique: A Classroom-Based Waste Management Strategy

Aniceto D. Garcia

Master Teacher II

Chloe Alwyn O. Valenzona

Teacher III

Maria Aillen A. Cabahug

Teacher III

Abstract.

This study focused on determining the usefulness of MAVAC Technique which utilized eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers among Grade 7 Durian and Makopa students of Baybay National High School in Baybay City, Leyte, Philippines. Specifically, it intended to determine the respondents' level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags before and after using them. It also aspired to determine whether or not there is a significant difference in their level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags before and after its actual use. In this research, a pretest-post-test approach to a Quasi-Experimental research design was utilized. Wilcoxon-Signed Rank Test was used in interpreting data. Results of this study revealed that the mean pretest score of the students is 3.08 which rose up to 4.62 in the post-test. It was also found out that there is a significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents at 1% level of significance. Findings of the study disclosed that the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers can be an effective means to solve/minimize the school's problem on solid waste management.

Keywords: eco-friendly bags; paper and plastic; Quasi-experimental; pretest; post-test

1.0 Introduction

Rationale

Waste, according to Gupta & Sharma (2023), pertains to anything which is considered as unwanted or no longer needed and is thrown away from households, industrial firms, or agricultural entities on a large scale. The major type of waste is solid waste which is characterized by being hard and occupies space such as plastics, woods, papers, and even food leftovers.

The three topmost sources of solid wastes around the world are China, India, and the USA (Nanda and Berruti, 2021). In India alone, 143,449 metric tons of solid wastes were produced daily in 2013 which rose up to 62 million tons annually in 2021 (Mohanty et al., 2022). It has also been projected that due to lack of a proper solid waste management system, the total volume of wastes in developing nations will skyrocket up to three times in 2050.

Karim and Wetterhan (2020) conducted a comparative study on solid waste management in the United States, Europe, and Asia where purposive sampling was used. Results showed that Europe

ranked first followed by the United States while Asia had the lowest score among the three. This shows that the Philippines, being a part of Asia, is still finding effective ways to solve this problem.

Since solid waste management deeply concerns the Filipinos, the Philippine Government enacted Republic Act (R.A.) 9003 or the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000. This act established a unique ecological way to manage solid wastes by supporting waste reduction, recycling, and proper waste disposal. Appropriate penalties for the violations are imposed and strengthened public awareness and participation in promoting a cleaner, greener, and healthier environment. Cadungog (2024) stressed out that the problem on solid waste management also concerns most schools in the Philippines. Fleming (2011) added that students need to look into their own habits, consider how this problem can be solved, and develop a sense of personal responsibility on waste segregation and its environmental impact.

In accordance with R.A. 9003, The Department of Education-Regional Office VIII issued Regional Memorandum No. 061, s. 2021 which underscored strict compliance to proper segregation of wastes in all public offices and schools. Schumpert and Dietz (2015) posits that the brimming trash cans require an immediate solution.

In Baybay National High School, different strategies had been lobbied by the school's SWM Team. However, based on their most recent report, there are still sections whose garbage was not properly segregated. According to the school's Supreme Student Government (SSG) Officers' report, plastics and used papers mixed up inside garbage bins.

The researchers were thinking that if the students will learn proper waste segregation and recycling at the classroom level, they will be encouraged to do the same in their respective homes and communities. This prompted them to propose MAVAC technique which is coined after the name of one of its implementer, Maria Aillen Valenzona Alkuino-Cabahug.

This proposed intervention is unique because it starts at the classroom level and if this study will yield a significant result, it will be proposed by the researchers that eco-friendly bags will be used by the students in other sections and even in other schools within the division.

Research Questions

This study focuses on the usefulness of eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers among Grade 7-Durian and Makopa students of Baybay National High School. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers before using them?
2. What is their level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers after experiencing their use?
3. Is there a significant difference in their level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags before and after their actual use?

2.0 Methodology

The ultimate goal of this study was to ascertain the usefulness of eco-friendly bags in recycling plastic wrappers and used dry paper among the Grade 7-Durian and Makopa students of Baybay National High School. Below are the necessary information and important steps done during the conduct of this research.

2.1 Research Design

This study follows the pretest-posttest approach to a Quasi-Experimental research design. Quasi-Experimental design was used in this research because the respondents are purposely assigned and not random.

2.2 Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants of this study were the 80 students of Grade 7-Durian and Makopa of Baybay National High School for the School Year 2024-2025. The sections were purposely chosen because they are located in one building and based on researchers' observation, their trash cans are almost always beaming with trash.

2.3 Data Gathering Procedure

Pre-Intervention

Prior to the conduct of the study, written consents were signed by the respondents' parents and they were assured that the results of this study were for research purposes only and the data were treated with utmost confidentiality.

Two sets of researcher-made questionnaires were used in this study: the pre-intervention questionnaire which solicited respondents' responses to the questions relating to their level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling before they were exposed to it and the post-intervention questionnaire which contained the same questions as the pre-intervention questionnaire but it was answered by the respondents after their exposure to the use of eco-friendly bags. The questionnaire was crafted by the researchers but was checked by competent master teachers and was subjected to Cronbach's Alpha with a rate of 0.81.

In order to make sure that the questionnaires were understood by the respondents, they were pretested using 5 students from another Grade 7 section who were asked to answer the questionnaire, tell whether or not the questions are easy to understand, and solicit their ideas on how it could be improved in preparation for the actual conduct of the research. Based on the results of the pre-testing, the questionnaires were revised and finalized.

Intervention Proper

During the day of the pre-intervention phase, the pre-intervention questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. The general directions on how to answer the questionnaire were provided to facilitate fast and easy answering. Sufficient time was set in answering the questionnaire and along the way, the researchers entertained questions that arose during the session.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), pp.69-77, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The intervention or the respondents' exposure to the use of eco-friendly bags lasted for a period of 2 quarters (third and fourth quarters of School Year 2024-2025). Each student in Grade 7-Durian and Makopa were given two eco-friendly bags with different colors. The said eco-friendly bags were mounted using thumb tacks at the back portion of their armchair for easy access. The first one was used to contain used dry paper while the second one was used to contain plastic wrappers. These two are the most common garbage in the classroom level.

Before going home every Friday, they are going to empty their eco-friendly bags. A big box was positioned at a designated part inside the classroom where they put their used dry papers. The papers were collected and were processed into a beneficial project. The students emptied the second eco-bag containing plastic wrappers, shredded them into pieces, and used them in making throw pillows.

In this particular study, the researchers determined the students' level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling then they were provided with the eco-friendly bags where they put their wastes (used dry papers and plastic wrappers) during the third and fourth quarters of School Year 2024-2025. After that, their level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling were measured again and determined whether or not there was a change in their level of attitude towards it and if their use of the eco-friendly bags was really effective in maintaining the cleanliness inside the classrooms.

Post-Intervention

After the respondents have answered the questionnaires, the same were collected and were made sure that all items were answered. This was made to ensure that data are complete and to ensure that the results will really speak the real voice of the respondents. After the two quarter duration of the intervention, the respondents were asked to answer the post-intervention questionnaire. Once the questionnaires were retrieved, the responses were tallied and results were interpreted and reported in relation to the research objectives.

2.4 Data Analysis Procedure

In order to determine the respondents' attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags before their exposure to its use, nine questions will also be asked. Their answers can always be, often, sometimes be, seldom, or never. For the positive questions: always will be given 5 points, often - 4 points, sometimes - 3 points, seldom - 2 points, and never - 1 point. Their mean scores will be classified as: 0-2.34 - low attitude level, 2.35-3.68 - moderate attitude level, and 3.69-5.00 - high attitude level. The pre-test mean will be compared with that of the post-test mean.

In order to determine if there is a significant difference on the respondents' level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags before and after its actual use, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was used to confirm that the difference between the pre-test and post-test is significant.

2.5 Ethical Considerations

The integrity of the conduct of this research study was based on the parents' formal permission.

During the actual conduct of the study, the objectives of the study were explained to the respondents. They were informed and given assurance that their participation in the conduct of the study were for research purposes only and their responses to the questions were treated with utmost confidentiality.

3.0 Results and Discussion

This study focused on the usefulness of eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers among Grade 7-Durian and Makopa students of Baybay National High School.

3.1 Respondents' Level of Attitude towards the Use of Eco-Friendly Bags in Recycling Used Dry Paper and Plastic Wrappers Before and After Using The MAVAC Technique

Based on the results of the study, as reflected in Table 1, the first statement "I think that using eco-friendly bags can really help in recycling used paper and in Solid Waste Management (SWM)." is the only statement among the 9 statements which yielded a weighted mean of 3.78 which is equivalent to a high level of attitude. This means that they already have the idea about recycling and SWM basically learned from their respective families and from the school. All other statements yielded either moderate or low attitude level.

Table 1. Respondents' level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers before and after using them

Statements	Pretest		Post-Test	
	Weighted Mean	Level of Attitude	Weighted Mean	Level of Attitude
1. I think that using eco-friendly bags can really help in recycling used paper and in Solid Waste Management (SWM).	3.78	High	4.48	High
2. I believe I can do something to keep our classroom clean by using eco-friendly bags.	3.41	Moderate	4.62	High
3. I believe that eco-friendly bags can be used in storing used paper and plastic.	3.27	Moderate	4.65	High
4. I am happy that I can help save Mother Earth through the use of eco-friendly bags.	3.59	Moderate	4.70	High
5. I feel proud of taking part in preserving nature by using eco-friendly bags inside the classroom.	3.34	Moderate	4.62	High
6. I want to help save the world from solid wastes so I will use eco-friendly bags.	3.52	Moderate	4.65	High
7. I should make sure that no paper and plastic will be improperly disposed inside the classroom.	2.20	Low	4.61	High

8. Whenever I see paper and plastic scattered in the classroom, I picked them up and put them inside eco-friendly bags.	2.44	Moderate	4.70	High
9. I promise to promote the use of eco-friendly bags in storing used paper and plastic to people around me.	2.20	Low	4.56	High
Overall	3.08	Moderate	4.62	High

Statement numbers 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 8 yielded weighted means which are equivalent to moderate level of attitude while the two remaining items (number 7 and number 9) yielded a low level of attitude. These two statements are in the psychomotor domain and their low weighted means that students do not have the intention to stay committed with SWM particularly on the use of eco-friendly bags inside the classroom.

Overall, during the pretest, the average weighted mean is 3.08 which is equivalent to moderate. In the post-test, however, the respondents answered positively and they have significantly improved their level of attitude from low and moderate to high (4.62).

3.2 Difference of the Respondents' Mean Scores Before and After the Intervention

While there was an increase in the respondents' level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers before and after using them, there is still a need to determine whether or not there is a significant difference in their level of attitude before and after being exposed to the MAVAC technique. In this particular research, the test statistic used was Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test to test the significant differences since the data set is ordinal and dependent.

Table 2. Overall pre-test and posttest attitude scores towards the use of eco-friendly bags (n=79)

Actual Use	Mean rank	SD	W	Z	p-value	Significance
Before	3.25	0.724	0.000	-7.222	<.001	Significant
After	4.85	0.361				

Data revealed that the mean post-test score (4.85) was significantly higher than the mean pretest score (3.25) which indicates that the level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags becomes significantly higher after the actual use. Also, the computed z-value confirms that there is a significant difference in their level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags before and after their actual use. This means that the use of eco-friendly bags in managing the paper and plastic wastes inside the classrooms has become effective. Results of this study are contradictory with the results of the study conducted by Mkhonto and Mnguni (2021) which showed that participating in a school-based recycling project did not enhance Grade 7 Natural Sciences learners' perceptions of, attitudes towards, and understanding of recycling. However, results of this study agreed with Piedad and Rubín (2024) who stated that teachers observed a significant reduction in classroom wastes among students. Parents even reported that these habits extended to the home environment.

4.0 Conclusion

After conducting the study, the researchers concluded that the respondents only have a moderate level of attitude (3.08) towards the use of eco-friendly bags before using eco-friendly bags which rose up to 4.62 (high level of attitude) after using the eco-friendly bags. It was also found out that there was a significant difference in the level of attitude towards the use of eco-friendly bags in recycling used dry paper and plastic wrappers before and after experiencing their use. The intervention was found effective in addressing the problem of solid waste management at the classroom level.

5.0 References

- Cadungog, J.R. (2024). Impact of R.A. 9003 on Environmental Management in the Philippines. Retrieved on September 6, 2025 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380793265_NameJhun_Robe_R_Cadungog_SectionBIT_CT3A_SubjectENVIRONMENTAL_WASTE_AND_MANAGEMENT_Case_Study_Impact_of_Republic_Act_No_9003_on_Environmental_Management_in_the_Philippines
- Fleming, Mike. (2011). Teaching the 3Rs: Reduce, Reuse, Recycle. Retrieved on June 15, 2019 from www.eco-schoolsni.org
- Gupta, P. & Sharma, A. (2023). Solid Waste Management (SWM) & Its Effect on Environment and Human Health. Retrieved on September 6, 2025 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373717054_Solid_Waste_Management_SWM_and_Its_Effect_on_Environment_Human_Health
- Karim, M.A. and Wetterhan, J.T. (2020). A Comparative Study of Solid Waste Management in the United States, Europe, and Asia. Retrieved on September 6, 2025 from <https://www.civilenvironjournal.com/articles/acee-aid1019.php>
- Lino, F. A., Ismail, K. A., & Castañeda-Ayarza, J. A. (2023). Municipal solid waste treatment in Brazil: A comprehensive review. *Energy Nexus*, 100232.
- Mkhonto, B. and Mnguni, L. (2021). The Impact of a Rural School-Based Solid Waste Management Project on Learners' Perceptions, Attitudes, and Understanding of Recycling. Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/2313-4321/6/4/71> on March 9, 2025
- Mohanty, S., Mishra, S., & Mohanty, A. (2022). Municipality Solid Waste Management. A Case Study of Smart City Bhubaneswar, Odisha. *Journal of Environmental Management & Tourism*, 13(5), 1361-1373.
- Nanda, S., & Berruti, F. (2021). Municipal solid waste management and landfilling technologies: a review. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*, 19, 1433-1456.
- Noll, Bernadette & Martinez, Jessica. (2018). How to Create a Zero Waste Classroom. Retrieved on June 15, 2019 from www.austineconetwork.org

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), pp.69-77, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Piedad, M. & Rubin, N. (2024). TRASH (Transformation and Resilience towards Advancing Sustainable Habits) Project: A Waste Management Classroom Innovation for Young Eco-Champions. Retrieved from <https://journalamr-inc.org/index.php/balangkasan/article/view/3> on March 9, 2025

Schumpert, Kary and Dietz, Cyndra. (2015). Zero Waste: A Realistic Sustainability Program for Schools. Retrieved on June 15, 2019 from www.ecocycle.org

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17292433

